

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.5.1: Biotic facilitation

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Description

Section 3.3.5.1 assesses the role of facilitative interactions among alien species along the invasional continuum for chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. It also addresses Invasional Meltdown as a consequence of multiple biotic facilitations I conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review that was further complemented and expanded with other sources suggested by both internal and external reviewers, and my own background and expertise on this topic, consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

I carried out a search in Scopus, read the title and when relevant, also the abstract of the 100 first titles of each search ordered by relevance, from the 31,756 documents found. I selected and downloaded a list of 26 potentially relevant papers. I read 19 of the 26 selected papers. The remaining 7 papers were not reviewed either because they were not available, or because after a more thorough reading of the abstract the topic was not directly relevant or was also covered in another related paper.

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review. No quantitative analysis was performed.

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms**

Edit

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("invasional meltdown" OR facilit* OR synerg* AND transport* OR introduc* OR invasi* OR spread* OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non-indigenous) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR re) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI"))

- **Search engine:**

Scopus

- Date

24/09/2019

- Overview of the search results and selection criteria

Number of search result:

26

Selection criteria:

I selected and downloaded a list of 26 potentially relevant papers. I read 19 of the 26 selected papers. The remaining 7 papers were not reviewed either because they were not available, or because after a more thorough reading of the abstract the topic was not directly relevant or was also covered in another related paper.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations):

13

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.)

Number of papers reviewed:

32 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)